

EXPRESSION OF THE PRETERITE FORM OF LIMITATIVE NEUTRAL VERBS IN GERMAN IN UZBEK

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Abstract: *This article comparatively examines the preterite forms of the past tense in German and Uzbek, as well as the aspectual and temporal meanings of the recent past tense in Uzbek, which is considered synonymous with the German preterite. It highlights the similarities, differences, and common features between these forms. Using examples based on materials from both languages, limitative neutral verbs are analyzed from an aspectual perspective. The main focus is on the differences and commonalities that emerge in tense forms during the process of translating from German into Uzbek.*

Keywords: *past tense, preterite, aspectual situation, terminative, processual, iterative, durative, limitative neutral verb, actional;*

Präteritum is derived from the Latin word "praeteritum," which denotes an event that occurred in the past. In English, it is referred to as "Preterite," "Past Tense," or "Imperfect Tense," while in French, it is known as "Preterite," "Passé simple," or "Imparfait." It is understood as a past tense form. In some languages, including traditional Greek grammar, the preterite is called "aorist." In modern German, it is termed "Präteritum," whereas in older grammatical literature, the term "Imperfekt" was used instead [Bussmann, 2002: 503].

As is known, Germanic languages, particularly German, distinguish between strong and weak verb groups. The preterite form is also formed differently for these verbs. Specifically, strong verbs form the preterite based on the ablaut series through the phenomenon of inflection (change of the vowel in the root), for example: *trinken - trank, schreiben - schrieb, biegen - bog, helfen - half*, and others. The preterite of weak verbs is formed by adding the suffix - (e) te to the verb stem: *machen - machte, melden - meldete, sagen - sagte*, etc. If we compare this phenomenon with the second language being analyzed, namely Uzbek, we can primarily consider the recent past tense as an equivalent form to the preterite in this language, since both of these forms express actions that occurred shortly before the moment of speech. The recent past tense in Uzbek is formed synthetically by adding the suffix *-di* to the verb stem: *keldi (came), o'qidi (read), yozdi (wrote), bordi (went)*, etc. Having examined the formation of past tense forms (preterite in German, recent past tense in Uzbek) in these two languages, we will now explore the meanings of these forms in various aspectual situations. At this point, it is appropriate to elaborate on the concept of "aspectual situation." The aspectual situation is not limited to aspectual meanings formed through various linguistic, grammatical, lexical, and contextual means (reaching/not reaching a limit, completeness/incompleteness, terminativity/processuality). It also encompasses aspectual meanings arising from modes of action (initiation, continuation, repetition, and resultative nature of an action) and their combinations [Muminova, 2021: 105]. Several types of aspectual

situations can be observed. For instance, the transition of an action from one state to another is inchoative, a repetitive action is iterative, an action in progress is processual, and an action that has reached its endpoint is a terminative aspectual situation. After providing an explanation of the concept of "aspectual situation," we will proceed directly to the analysis of preterital aspectual situations.

As mentioned above, this article analyzes the aspectual meanings of verbs with a limitative neutral character. At this point, it is worth discussing the actional nature of verbs. All verbs existing in the language are aspectually divided into three major groups (bounded, unbounded, and limitative neutral verbs). In the lexical semantics of a bounded verb, there is an internal boundary of action, while unbounded verbs lack this internal boundary. Limitative neutral verbs simultaneously embody two opposing meanings of boundedness and unboundedness. Below, we will highlight the meanings of verbs with these two actional characteristics in aspectual situations. We will observe examples starting with mental activity verbs, particularly the limitative neutral verb "**denken**" (to think):(1) Wilhelm thought angrily that this would continue like this until the end of his days [Seghers, 51]. (1a) Wilhelm **dachte** wütend, daß das dann immer weiter so gehen sollte bis ans Ende seiner Tage "*Vilgelm g'azab bilan: „Hayotimning oxirigacha bu shunday davom etaverishi kerakmi“ - deb o'yladi.* (Wilhelm **thought** angrily that this would continue like this until the end of his days).[By the author]. - The examples reflect the durative aspect of the thought process, which continues for a certain period. Neither the beginning nor the end point of the action in the sentence is known; therefore, a procedural aspectual situation has occurred here. The elements *immer - always, bis ans Ende seiner Tage - until the end of his days, weiter gehen - continue* - in the examples also reinforce the meaning of the continuity of the action. In both languages, the use of the same tense form (preterite) and the recent past tense also correspond to each other.

The verb "**denken**" (to think) with two actional semantics participates in a terminative aspectual situation through a completed action in the subsequent example: (2) "Im Geschäft ist er doch ganz anders," **dachte** er, "wie er hier breit sitzt und die Arme über der Brust kreuzt" *Do'konda u tamoman boshqacha, bu yerda-chi, u qo'llarini ko'ksiga chalishtirib, gerdayib o'tiribdi*“, **hayolidan o'tkazdi** Georg [Kafka, 10]. (2a) "In the shop he is completely different, but here he sits with his arms crossed over his chest," Georg **thought** [Kafka, 30]. - In the sentence in both languages, a completed action is given (*dachte* - the act of thinking occurred and was completed in the past). In the Uzbek example, thinking is expressed in the form of *xayolidan o'tkazmoq, not o'ylamoq (to think)*. The similarity lies in the fact that the same tense form is used in both languages (preterit - recent past tense).

After the analysis of the verb **denken** with two actional semantics, we see aspectual situations with the participation of tell. In the next example, terminativity is reflected. Let's look at an example:(3) Wenn du nachdenkst, mußst du dich erinnern. Er **erzählte** damals unglaubliche Geschichten von der russischen Revolution [Kafka, 14]. (3a) *Obdan o'ylab ko'ring, esingizga tushadi. U o'shanda rus inqilobi xususida aqlga sig'maydigan qissalarni qilgandi.* (Think carefully, and it will come back to you. At that time, he **told incredible stories** about the Russian revolution) [Kafka, 33]. The given examples describe the process of storytelling that occurred and was

completed in the past. It is more appropriate to translate the verb "**erzählen**" into Uzbek not as "*qissalarni qilgandi*," but as "*hikoyalarni so'zlagandi*." In German, the preterite form is used, while in Uzbek, the distant past tense is employed.

In the following example, "**erzählen**" participates in a procedural aspectual situation with an unlimited function. Let's observe the example: (4) *Maria erzählte zögernd auf Geschkens Fragen von ihren Leuten in Pellworm* [Seghers, 61]. (4a) *Mariya uyalib Pellvormdagi qarindosh-urug'lari haqida hikoya qilar edi*. (*Maria hesitantly told about her relatives in Pellworm in response to Geschken's questions*) [Zegers, 76]. In both examples, an unfinished, continuous action in the durative aspect is presented. The adverb of manner *zögernd* (*hesitantly, reluctantly*) used in the German sentence indicates that the action occurs slowly and extends over a certain period of time, confirming the durativity in the sentence. The aspectual meaning corresponds between the two languages, with the preterite used in German and the past continuous form used in Uzbek.

There is also an actional contradiction in the semantics of the German verb **erklären** (to explain). Compare: (5) *Der Freund war nun schon über drei Jahre nicht in der Heimat gewesen und erklärte dies sehr notdürftig mit der Unsicherheit der politischen Verhältnisse in Rußland, die demnach also auch die kürzeste Abwesenheit eines kleinen Geschäftsmannes nicht zuließen,...* [Kafka, 4]. (5a) *Do'stining vatanidan ketib qolganiga uch yildan oshib ketgandi, shuni ham zo'rg'a mavhum tarzda izohlarkan, go'yo Rossiyada qandaydir mubham siyosiy ahvol humkron bo'lib, mayda savdogarlar qisqagina muddatga ham biror yoqqa chiqolmaydi*. (*It had been over three years since his friend had left his homeland, and he barely managed to explain this vaguely, as if some ambiguous political situation prevailed in Russia, and small merchants could not leave even for a short time*) [Kafka, 25]. - In the German language example, a process (explanation) that occurred once in the past and was completed is described. In the Uzbek language, the meaning of an action that continues for a certain period of time is conveyed. The continuity in the sentence is reflected through the past continuous tense form *-ar-*. Thus, in German, the preterite is used, while in Uzbek, the past continuous tense form is employed.

In the following example, "**erklären**" (to explain) creates a procedural aspectual situation through an unlimited action: (6) *Worauf der Nadler von neuem erklärte, warum gerade jetzt solche Männer wie er in Berlin vonnöten seien* [Seghers, 47]. (6a) *Nadler esa, yana cholga, nima uchun unga o'xshagan odamlar hozir Berlinda judayam zarur ekanliklarini tushuntirishga urindi*. *Nadler, however, again attempted to explain to the old man why people like him were so desperately needed in Berlin now* [Zegers, 60]. Although the sentence reflects a one-time action, it carries the meaning of continuity and incompleteness in the past tense. This is because it is unclear whether the action has reached its final point. The use of the same forms (preterite - recent past tense) in both languages is a similarity.

In the following examples, aspectual situations involving the verb "**schreiben**" are analyzed: (7) *Georg schrieb ihm aber solche Dinge viel lieber, als daß er zugestanden hätte, daß er selbst vor einem Monat mit einem Fräulein Frieda Brandenfeld, einem Mädchen aus wohlhabender Familie, sich verlobt hatte* [Kafka, 6]. (7a) *Georg do'stiga o'zi e'tirof etganidek, hatto bir oy avval o'ziga to'q oilaga*

mansub bo'lgan qiz, Frida Brandenfeld ismli xonim bilan unashirilgani xususida yozishni niyat qilgandi. (Georg would rather **write** such things to his friend than admit that he himself had become engaged a month ago to Miss Frieda Brandenfeld, a girl from a wealthy family) [Kafka, 26]. - The German example illustrates an ongoing process in the imperfective aspect. In the Uzbek language, "schrieb" - having a future-oriented meaning (he intended to write) - is reflected as an unrealized future wish or intention. The verb "yozmoq"(to write) is realized in the form of an action noun.

In the next example to be analyzed (8), the limitative neutral "schreiben" (to write) serves as a limitation in a terminative aspectual situation: (8) *Und tatsächlich berichtete er seinem Freunde in dem langen Brief, den er an diesem Sonntagvormittag **schrieb**, die erfolgte Verlobung mit folgenden Worten: „Die beste Neuigkeit habe ich mir bis zum Schluß aufgespart* [Kafka, 7]. (8a) *U ushbu yakshanba kuni ertalab **yozgan** uzundan-uzoq xatida haqiqatdan bama'ni qiz bilan unashirilganini shunday bayon etgandi: „Eng yoqimli xabarni oxirigacha pinhon tutdim.“* (In the lengthy letter he **wrote** this Sunday morning, he truly described his engagement to a sensible girl as follows: "I kept the most pleasant news hidden until the end.") [Kafka, 27]. - In the examples from both languages, an action completed in the distant past - terminativity - is reflected. The terminativity in the example arose under the influence of the temporal indicator in the sentence (*an diesem Sonntagvormittag* - *this Sunday morning*). This is because the subject had completed the writing action much earlier. A distinctive feature is that the German preterite is rendered in Uzbek using the affix of the distant past tense (**-gan**).

Next, two actional characteristics of the verb "tragen" are analyzed. In the example, the limitative neutral character expresses the terminative in the function of constraint. Let's look at an example: (9) *Er **trug** das Gepäck in die Bahnhofswirtschaft. Der Mann versprach ihm ein Trägergeld, wenn er ihn um zwölf Uhr am selben Tisch abhole* [Seghers, 223]. (9a) *U buyumlarni bufetga **eltib berdi**. Noma'lum kishi, agar Gans soat o'n ikkida manashu stolga yetib kelguday bo'lsa, qilgan mehnatining evaziga unga haq to'lashni va'da qildi.* He delivered the items to the buffet. The unknown person promised to pay Hans for his work if he arrived at this table at twelve o'clock [Zegers, 257]. - The sentence conveys the meaning of an action that occurs and is completed. Terminativity in the sentence can also be understood through the following sentence. Because, in the second sentence, it is stated that if the boy performs such service again, he will be paid. We understand this with the help of extralinguistic factors. In the Uzbek example, terminativity is also formed under the influence of a completed action. The completeness here stems from the relationship between the main and auxiliary verbs; that is, this analytical form (**eltib berdi**) clearly shows that the object has reached its intended destination. Another common feature is that both examples use the same tense forms (preterite and recent past tense). In the next example, the procedural aspect is given. The procedurality in the example is expressed through the semantics of the verb "tragen": (10) *"Er **trug** Militärstiefel und eine alte Jacke, bloß mit dem Abzeichen seiner Garde im Knopfloch und seinem Eisernen Kreuz* [Seghers, 46]. (10a) *Uning oyog'ida harbiycha etik bo'lib, **ustidagi** eski kalta kamzulining yoqasiga ko'ngilli otryad*

znachogi va ko'ragiga „Temir krest“ taqilgan edi (He wore military boots and an old jacket, with only the badge of his guard in the buttonhole and his Iron Cross) [Zegers, 58-59]. The action of *tragen* (to wear) in the example reflects a continuous, clearly unbounded process. This is because this verb denotes an ongoing action that extends over a certain period of time and does not end abruptly, indicating a continuous action. In the Uzbek sentence, the concept of wearing is conveyed not through the word "tragen" (to wear), but through lexical units meaning "on the feet" and "on top." (*oyog'ida, ustidagi*) These words imply the act of wearing certain clothes. In German, the preterite form is used, while in Uzbek, the distant past tense is employed.

According to the analysis of verbs with two actional properties in aspectual situations, these verbs in the preterite are realized in various forms of the past tense in the Uzbek language. Specifically, they are expressed through the recent past tense with the affix *-di*, the adverbial participle *-ib + -di*, the continuous past tense (*-ar edi; -yotgan*), the narrative past tense (*-ibdi*), and compound verbs formed with the adverbial participle (*-ib*) + *-di*.

Conclusion. The aspectual analysis of limitative neutral verbs belonging to various semantic groups revealed the following:

1. When verbs with dual actional semantics are used in a limited sense, they primarily participate in a terminative aspectual situation through completed actions.

2. Conversely, when such characteristic verbs are used in an unlimited sense, they express a procedural aspectual situation in the durative aspect, influenced by incomplete, continuous, or repetitive actions.

As a result of the conducted analysis, the following **similarities and differences** between the German preterite and its corresponding recent past tense forms in the Uzbek language **were identified**:

1. The use of both forms to express an event that occurred shortly before the moment of speech is their common feature: *Sie ging nach Hause - U uyiga ketdi. (He went home)*

2. From the point of view of structure, both are synthetic: *fragen - fragte; so'ramoq - so'radi; (to ask- asked)*.

3. At the same time, strong verbs in the preterit can also form the past tense form by changing the vowel in the root according to the law of inflection: *gehen - ging, fahren - fuhr...* but in the Uzbek language, such a situation is not observed.

4. From an aspectual point of view, some verbs in preterite reflect the duration of the action, the state: *Sie war krank.* (continued status displayed). The recent past in most cases expresses a completed action: *Men uni ko'rdim. (I saw it), (the action is completed).*

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